

The Second Dissociation Constant of Sulphuric Acid at a Number of Temperatures and Heat of Dissociation of HSO_4^- Ion

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The second dissociation constant of sulphuric acid has been determined from the study of the cell

where Q.H. stands for quinhydrone. The e.m.f. of the above cell is given by

$$E = E_0 + \frac{RT}{F} \ln [\text{H}^+][\text{Cl}^-]f_{\text{H}^+}f_{\text{Cl}^-}$$

The values of $f_{\text{H}^+}f_{\text{Cl}^-}$ at various ionic strengths and E_0 for the above cell are found from the study of the cell $\text{Hg}|\text{Hg}_2\text{Cl}_2|\text{HCl}(c)|\text{HCl}(c)|\text{HCl}(c)|\text{Q.H.}|\text{Pt}$. The concentration of Cl^- in the cell containing mixtures of acids is equal to stoichiometric concentration of hydrochloric acid. From the e.m.f. of the cell containing mixtures of acids, the values of $[\text{H}^+]$, $[\text{HSO}_4^-]$ and $[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]$ are found by method of successive approximations. With these values of concentrations at various ionic strengths, thermodynamic dissociation constant of HSO_4^- has been found to be 0.023, 0.016, 0.011 and 0.0083 at 5°, 15°, 25° and 35° respectively. From the above values of K the heat of dissociation of $\text{HSO}_4^- = \text{H}^+ + \text{SO}_4^{2-}$ comes out to be -5200 ± 300 Cals.

A number of workers namely Hamer¹, Davies, Jones and Monk², Nair and Nancollas³, Covington, Dobson and Wynne-Jones⁴ have studied the dissociation of the HSO_4^- ion by e.m.f. method in cells having no liquid junction potential. Hamer¹ has used Debye-Hückel⁵ equation with the second term of Bronsted⁶ equation, i.e., $\log f = -AZ^2\sqrt{\mu} + \beta\mu$ which may for convenience be called Debye-Hückel Brönsted equation, where A is the constant determined from the Debye-Hückel theory and β is a constant⁶ which cannot be derived from any theory. Davies, Jones and Monk² as well as Nair and Nancollas³ have used Davies⁷ empirical equation, $-\log f = AZ^2 \left(\frac{\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} - 0.2\mu \right)$ for calculating activity coefficients, where as Wynne-Jones and coworkers have used Debye-Hückel modified equation $-\log f = AZ^2 \frac{\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \rho\sqrt{\mu}}$, where A has the same significance as above and ρ is almost unity found by trial. The Debye-Hückel Brönsted equation has also been used in the present work for calculating the activity coefficients. Davies and coworkers⁸ have found out that Na_2SO_4

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2. C. W. Davies, H. W. Jones and C. B. Monk, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1921, 48, 1952.
3. V. S. K. Nair and G. H. Nancollas, *J.C.S.*, 1958, 4144.
4. A. K. Covington, J. V. Dobson and W. F. K. Wynne-Jones, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1965, 61, 2058.
5. P. Debye and E. Hückel, *Physik. Z.*, 1923, 24, 185 and 334.
6. J. N. Brönsted, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 44, 938.
7. C. W. Davies, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 2093.
8. E. C. Righellato and C. ff. Davies, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1930, 26, 592.

is incompletely dissociated. Hamer¹ has used solutions of Na₂SO₄, NaHSO₄ and NaCl in his cells where as Wynne-Jones and coworkers⁴ used solutions of NaHSO₄ and Na₂SO₄. None of them have taken into account the possible formation of NaSO₄⁻ ion. Nair and Nancollas³ who used a mixture of HCl and H₂SO₄ as we have done, utilised Davies⁷ equation for calculating activity coefficients. We have avoided using this equation because its validity has been questioned⁹. The earlier workers did not follow, whereas we have followed, a method by which the thermodynamic dissociation constant can be found by extrapolating apparent values of dissociation constant to zero ionic strength.

EXPERIMENTAL

In the present investigation the dissociation constant of HSO₄⁻ ion has been determined by measuring the e.m.f. of the cell

As is evident from the design of the cell, there is no liquid junction potential. The bridge has been used only to avoid quinhydrone and mercurous chloride coming in contact with each other. Sulphuric and Hydrochloric acids used were of analytical grade. Separate stock solutions of the two in double distilled water were prepared, and standardised against borax¹⁰. Experimental solutions were prepared by mixing the two stock solutions in proper proportion and diluting with double distilled water to appropriate volume at the experimental temperatures. For the preparation of calomel and setting up of the calomel electrode, the method of Hills and Ives¹¹ was followed except that silicone treatment was not done. The electrode vessels, bridges and setting up of cells were similar to those published in an earlier paper¹². The temperature of thermostat was controlled within $\pm 0.05^\circ$. Measurements were made with a Bajaj Vernier Potentiometer which gave the same readings as Tinsley Vernier Potentiometer. Duplicate experiments in each case were performed and the duplicates mostly agreed amongst themselves within 0.1 mv. In a few cases the difference was 0.15 mv. The e.m.f. given in the tables are mean of the two. The experimental data along with apparent dissociation constant $K_A = \frac{[\text{H}^+][\text{SO}_4^{2-}]}{[\text{HSO}_4^-]}$, are given in tables I, II, III and IV. Stoichiometric concentration is indicated by []_T.

TABLE I
Temp. 5°

Mixture of HCl and H ₂ SO ₄		<i>E.</i> in volt.	[H ⁺] × 10 ³	[HSO ₄ ⁻] × 10 ⁴	[SO ₄ ²⁻] × 10 ⁴	μ × 10 ⁴	K _A × 10 ²	log K _A - 4A√ <i>i</i>
[HCl] _T	[H ₂ SO ₄] _T							
0.004	0.002	0.18776	7.666	3.34	16.66	93.32	3.8238	$\bar{2}.39233$
0.005	0.005	0.20542	13.539	14.61	35.39	170.78	3.2796	$\bar{2}.25864$
0.010	0.010	0.23608	26.001	39.99	60.01	320.02	3.9017	$\bar{2}.23913$
0.020	0.010	0.25933	35.198	48.02	51.98	403.96	3.8101	$\bar{2}.18529$
0.020	0.015	0.26333	42.610	73.90	76.10	502.20	4.3878	$\bar{2}.20117$
0.020	0.020	0.26669	49.970	100.30	99.70	599.40	4.9670	$\bar{2}.21419$
0.025	0.025	0.27611	60.200	148.00	102.00	704.00	4.1489	$\bar{2}.09567$

9. (i) G. A. H. Elton, *Discussion of the Faraday Soc.*, 1957, **24**, 114.

(ii) E. A. Guggenheim (In the same discussion), 1957, **24**, 63.

10. A. I. Vogel—Quantitative Inorganic Analysis (Third Edition), 1962, 238, (Section—11, 12).

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12. S. Nath, S. Aditya and B. Prasad, *This Journal*, 1951, **28**, 683.

TABLE II

Mixture of HCl and H ₂ SO ₄		Temp. 15°						
[HCl] _T	[H ₂ SO ₄] _T	<i>E.</i> in volt.	[H ⁺] × 10 ³	[HSO ₄ ⁻] × 10 ⁴	[SO ₄ ²⁻] × 10 ⁴	μ × 10 ⁴	K _A × 10 ⁵	log K _A - 4A√μ
0.0005	0.0005	0.08297	1.458	0.425	4.575	19.150	1.5690	$\bar{2}.10808$
0.002	0.001	0.14019	3.833	1.674	8.326	46.652	1.9060	$\bar{2}.14349$
0.004	0.002	0.17281	7.482	5.178	14.822	89.644	2.1414	$\bar{2}.14133$
0.005	0.005	0.19120	13.282	17.180	32.820	165.700	2.5370	$\bar{2}.14631$
0.020	0.010	0.24707	34.616	53.840	46.160	392.320	2.9700	$\bar{2}.07680$
0.020	0.020	0.25399	47.545	124.540	75.460	551.000	2.8820	$\bar{3}.99023$
0.025	0.025	0.26418	58.546	164.525	85.475	671.000	3.0420	$\bar{3}.96479$

TABLE III

Mixture of HCl and H ₂ SO ₄		Temp. 25°						
[HCl] _T	[H ₂ SO ₄] _T	<i>E.</i> in volt.	[H ⁺] × 10 ³	[HSO ₄ ⁻] × 10 ⁴	[SO ₄ ²⁻] × 10 ⁴	μ × 10 ⁴	K _A × 10 ²	log K _A - 4A√μ
0.0005	0.0005	0.06576	1.442	0.576	4.424	18.848	1.1078	$\bar{3}.9560$
0.002	0.001	0.12487	3.783	2.166	7.834	45.668	1.3684	$\bar{3}.9986$
0.004	0.002	0.15855	7.372	6.281	13.719	87.610	1.5905	$\bar{2}.0109$
0.005	0.005	0.17718	12.899	20.845	29.155	158.270	1.7852	$\bar{3}.9954$
0.020	0.010	0.23515	33.785	62.150	37.850	375.660	2.0575	$\bar{3}.9188$
0.020	0.020	0.24191	45.511	144.890	55.110	510.100	1.7311	$\bar{3}.7886$
0.025	0.025	0.25272	56.794	182.060	67.940	635.880	2.1194	$\bar{3}.8126$

TABLE IV

Mixture of HCl and H ₂ SO ₄		Temp. 35°						
[HCl] _T	[H ₂ SO ₄] _T	<i>E.</i> in volt.	[H ⁺] × 10 ³	[HSO ₄ ⁻] × 10 ⁴	[SO ₄ ²⁻] × 10 ⁴	μ × 10 ⁴	K _A × 10 ²	log K _A - 4A√μ
0.0005	0.0005	0.04906	1.428	0.716	4.284	18.568	0.8546	$\bar{3}.8422$
0.002	0.001	0.11020	3.755	2.455	7.545	45.090	1.1539	$\bar{3}.9227$
0.004	0.002	0.14484	7.266	7.342	12.658	85.319	1.2527	$\bar{3}.9061$
0.005	0.005	0.16395	12.613	23.870	26.130	152.260	1.3807	$\bar{3}.8839$
0.020	0.010	0.22380	33.208	67.920	32.080	364.160	1.5624	$\bar{3}.7976$
0.020	0.020	0.23111	45.609	143.920	56.080	512.160	1.7772	$\bar{3}.7799$
0.025	0.025	0.24185	55.965	190.350	59.650	619.300	1.7538	$\bar{3}.7273$

DISCUSSION

The e.m.f. of the cell :

is given by

$$E = E_0 + \frac{2 \cdot 303}{F} \frac{RT}{T} \log[\text{H}^+][\text{Cl}^-]f_{\text{HfCl}} \quad (1)$$

$$\text{or} \quad \frac{F(E - E_0)}{2 \cdot 303 RT} = \log[\text{H}^+][\text{Cl}^-]f_{\text{HfCl}} \quad (1)$$

The activity coefficient can be expressed by

$$-\log f_{\text{HfCl}} = 2A\sqrt{\mu} - 2\beta\mu \quad (2)$$

The value A is known from Debye-Hückel theory and that of β was determined from the study of the cell : $\text{Hg} \left| \text{Hg}_2\text{Cl}_2 \quad \text{HCl} \right| \text{HCl} \left| \text{HCl} \quad \text{Q.H.} \right| \text{Pt}$. reported in an earlier paper¹³.
(c) | (c) | (c)

The equation (2) takes the following forms :—

$$-\log f_{\text{HfCl}} = 0.9842\sqrt{\mu} - 1.24484\mu \quad (2-1) \text{ at } 5^\circ$$

$$-\log f_{\text{HfCl}} = 1.0004\sqrt{\mu} - 1.2604\mu \quad (2-2) \text{ at } 15^\circ$$

$$-\log f_{\text{HfCl}} = 1.0178\sqrt{\mu} - 1.3018\mu \quad (2-3) \text{ at } 25^\circ$$

$$-\log f_{\text{HfCl}} = 1.0380\sqrt{\mu} - 1.2500\mu \quad (2-4) \text{ at } 35^\circ$$

In activity coefficients omitting the charge of the ion does not create any confusion. So it has been omitted. Thus f_{H} has been written in place of f_{H^+} and so on. Hydrochloric acid is completely dissociated and Cl^- does not combine with any other ion when mixed with sulphuric acid. Therefore $[\text{Cl}^-]$ is equal to $[\text{HCl}]_T$ in the mixtures of the acids. Sulphuric acid dissociates according to the following scheme :

If α is the degree of dissociation of HSO_4^- in the mixture of hydrochloric and sulphuric acids of stoichiometric concentrations c_1 and c_2 respectively, then $[\text{H}^+] = c_1 + c_2(1 + \alpha)$, $[\text{HSO}_4^-] = (1 - \alpha)c_2$ and $[\text{SO}_4^{2-}] = \alpha c_2$. In equation (1) all the terms except $[\text{H}^+]$ and f_{HfCl} are known. These are found by method of successive approximations. An arbitrary value is given to the ionic strength (μ). From this arbitrary μ , the corresponding value of f_{HfCl} is calculated from the appropriate equation (2-1) to (2-4), depending on the temperature of the experiment. The corresponding value of $[\text{H}^+]$ is calculated from equation (1). With thus determined value of $[\text{H}^+]$ the corresponding value of α is calculated from $[\text{H}^+] = c_1 + (1 + \alpha)c_2$. The corresponding values of $[\text{HSO}_4^-]$ and $[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]$ are calculated from $[\text{HSO}_4^-] = (1 - \alpha)c_2$ and $[\text{SO}_4^{2-}] = \alpha c_2$. A new value of μ can thus be calculated from ; $\mu = \frac{1}{2}[\text{H}^+] + \frac{1}{2}[\text{HSO}_4^-] + \frac{1}{2}[\text{Cl}^-] + 2[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]$. The whole process is repeated till $[\text{H}^+]$, $[\text{HSO}_4^-]$, $[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]$

and μ become constant within the experimental error. These final values represent the correct values of concentrations in the experimental solutions and are given in Tables I to IV.

$$\text{Now, } K = \frac{[\text{H}^+][\text{SO}_4^{2-}]}{[\text{HSO}_4^-]} \times \frac{f\text{H} \times f\text{SO}_4}{f\text{HSO}_4}$$

$$\text{or } K = K_A \times \frac{f\text{H} \times f\text{SO}_4}{f\text{HSO}_4}$$

$$\text{or } \log K = \log K_A + \log f\text{H} + \log f\text{SO}_4 - \log f\text{HSO}_4$$

Using Debye-Hückel Brönsted equation, we get;

$$\log K = \log K_A - 4A\sqrt{\mu} + (B_1 + B_2 - B_3)\mu$$

$$\text{of } \log K_A - 4A\sqrt{\mu} = \log K - \beta\mu \quad (3)$$

where $\beta = B_1 + B_2 - B_3$.

The value of K_A in the different mixtures of hydrochloric and sulphuric acids is calculated from the values of $[\text{H}^+]$, $[\text{SO}_4^{2-}]$ and $[\text{HSO}_4^-]$. The left hand side of the equation (3) is plotted against μ . A straight line is obtained which when extrapolated to $\mu = 0$ gives $\log K$. The straight line is so drawn that if all the adjacent points are joined, equal areas lie above and below the straight line. Very few of the points depart from the line to an extent which is beyond the experimental error. The value of β is calculated from the slope of the straight line. The results at 5°, 15°, 25° and 35° can be represented by the equations (3-1), (3-2), (3-3) and (3-4) respectively.

$$\log K_A = \bar{2}\cdot360 + 1\cdot9684\sqrt{\mu} - 3\cdot64706\mu \quad (3-1)$$

$$\log K_A = \bar{2}\cdot200 + 2\cdot0008\sqrt{\mu} - 3\cdot41176\mu \quad (3-2)$$

$$\log K_A = \bar{2}\cdot035 + 2\cdot0368\sqrt{\mu} - 3\cdot35294\mu \quad (3-3)$$

$$\log K_A = \bar{3}\cdot920 + 2\cdot0760\sqrt{\mu} - 3\cdot33340\mu \quad (3-4)$$

The experimental work of Hamer¹ is of a very high order. It is perhaps superior to ours. Hamer¹ has however used the equation

$$\log K_2 - 2\beta\mu = \log m_H + \log m_{\text{SO}_4} - \log m_{\text{HSO}_4} - 4A\sqrt{\mu}$$

upto ionic strength greater than 0.4. This equation is based on $\log fi = -Azi^2\sqrt{\mu} + \beta i/\mu$ which holds good only upto $\mu = 0.1$. This has introduced certain errors in the calculation of 'K'. Hamer has given the full experimental results only at 25° in his paper. On recalculating the value of K_2 by our method and confining ourselves to $\mu < 0.1$, the value of 'K₂' is found to be same as ours.

If Hamer's value at other temperatures are calculated they may also agree with our values. The great variation is ΔH in the work of Hamer from temperature to temperature (—146 at 0° and—5811 at 60°) made us feel that his 'K' values require recalculation.

The heat of dissociation of HSO_4^- ion has also been calculated by plotting our values of $\log K$ against $1/T$. The slope of the straight line obtained is given by $\frac{-\Delta H}{R \times 2.303}$ from which ΔH is calculated. The value of ΔH comes to -5238 ± 300 cal, in round numbers -5200 ± 300 cal. This value agrees fairly well with the values of Nancollas³, -5600 ± 200 cal., and that of Pitzer¹⁴, -5200 ± 500 cal. From the above plot the extrapolated values at K at 0° and 45° come to 0.0263 and 0.0063 mole/litre. It may be mentioned that we have avoided (1) the use of empirical equation of Davies⁷, (2) use of sodium sulphate because there is difference of opinion whether it is completely dissociated. We worked over a fairly wide range of ionic strength so that extrapolation to zero ionic strength becomes possible. Hence our values of K may be considered to be most reliable. For comparison, the values of K obtained from e.m.f. measurements by various authors are tabulated below.

TABLE V
Value of $K \times 10^2$ (mole/litre)

Name of the authors	Temperature °C					
	0	5	15	25	35	45
Davies, Jones and Monk ²	—	1.73	1.43	1.03	0.78	—
Recalculated by Nair and Nancollas ³	—	1.90	1.56	1.09	0.80	—
Hamer ¹	1.48	1.43	1.34	1.20	1.05	0.89
Hamer's value (Recalculated by Sharma and Prasad)	—	—	—	1.10	—	—
Wynne-Jones and workers ⁴	—	—	—	1.09	—	—
Nair and Nancollas ³	2.62	2.31	1.59	1.10	0.82	0.60
Present work	+2.63	2.30	1.60	1.10	0.83	+0.63

+ Extrapolated values.

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